

THE CHILDREN OF YOUNG AGE DEVELOPMENT OF
KNOWLEDGE PROCESSES THROUGH THE GAME

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Annotation: The contents of the article is aimed at developing modern methodological approaches to games, organizational development, and developing methodological development methods for children from today's preschool age.

Keywords: Poline oral creation of folks, mental development, competencies, intellectual potential, game educational activities.

Today, a large-scale reforms are being made in the preschool system for the preschool education for quality preschool education. The main goal of all reforms in the field is to create conditions for all respective intellectual, moral, aesthetic, and physical development of children with the future of our country.

The game of preschool children is diverse. Their types of game can mainly classify the following. 1) Watching games, divided into plot and roles; 2) diamelt games; 3) moving or rule games; 4) mixed games; 5) Cing and making games.

Games played as plots and roles are the oldest game form of age children. Preschool-age guests play games such as "kindergart-link", "Train Train". But even if children of children of different ages are the same, the plot will be different.

The role of the didactic games for preschool children are large. Didactic games are a great help to successfully conduct training on the basis of a special program in a preschool, to prepare a large group of children for school training. The moving or rule games are also important within preschool children. This is because the movies will physically fit children, encourages children to be courageous, frightened, agile. In children, the initiative, teams, and duty. It is "who's first", "copy", "scratched the white rabbit" and includes "Ethnows". The moving games are mainly conducted in walk and physical education sessions. They also play dried games in love. These games are placed on a variety of fairytes and stories, and roles are played directly.

Building-making games between preschool children will be all aimed at everyone. The activities of game allow you to study children individually. Some children like to play a team affect the general development of the psychological child. Therefore, the educators need to play the team. The role of the game in the development of child psyche is invaluable. We are hard to imagine the child's mental development without a game. Because through the game, the child develops not only physically, but also in a psychiadous part. Through the game, the child not only studies the events, what is in it does not learn the events, the characteristics, to

imagine speech, to imagine, to think, to work, to work, to work, to work, to work, to work, behavior. Many psychologists and teachers have focused on the psychological issues of the game, and the importance of the games in the psychic development of the game. It is known that the game is to reflect reality for child. This reality is much fun to the reality of the child. The curiosity of the game is easy to realize it. The activity in adult life is the significance of work, it can play the same importance in a child's life. It is possible to meditate on world psychological information, based on the rich data accumulated in the subject of world psychology. First of all, first of all, first when the action of the movement in preschool children, first of all, the organization of the game creates the most favorable conditions for growing and improving the movement of the same age. Second, the reason for the game affects the child's movement is that the entity of the movement is absorbed by the entity through direct training during the game. Third, the later development of the game creates the most favorable conditions for all processes. Therefore, the activity of game activities will be the active goal of increasing the activity of the child from the means of acting. After all, he is growing to the level of the initial object of an entity (creature) to the entity (creature). A pre-school child chooses a role with a certain feature, while it seeks to consciously perform the strict behavior of this or that character. Therefore, the game will turn into the most necessary operation for this child and turn into reality clearly possible that the possible possibility of new forms, improvement, and remembering them. From the conditions of the child's games, the conscious purpose of the game is reflected to perform the actions and its goal is to remember and remind the recall process. The child will be able to remember more words and remember more in the games against the laboratory conditions, which will help open the voluntary memory feature. The analysis of data collected in the experience allows: a) selection of a certain role by the child in the game and requires the process of remembering a lot of information; b) Therefore, the conscious purpose of the personijng of the character, repeating his actions, appears more on child and easily will fulfill. The game does not necessarily improve the process of knowledge but also affix the behavior of the child.

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